

TITLE

Magnetization Reversal Mechanisms in Highly Corrugated Thin Films

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ABSTRACT

Nanopatterned ferromagnetic (FM) thin films have specific characteristics that make them a workhorse for sensors based on magnonic, magnetoplasmonic or anisotropic magneto-resistive effects. Undulated FM thin films have been studied because of their tunable uniaxial anisotropy. They have been traditionally understood by means of Schlömann's model taking account of shape-induced magnetic anisotropies in softly corrugated systems. Here we show how it cannot describe accurately the magnetic behavior of highly corrugated FM systems within a thickness region of less than the ripple amplitude. We report on the magnetization reversal processes detected in permalloy films deposited onto highly corrugated patterns (250 nm in periodicity, 180 nm in amplitude) in a wide thickness range (15 to 150 nm), finding both that the anisotropy of the system does not correspond to a uniaxial type for FM thicknesses larger than 40 nm and that the anisotropy of the system increases with the FM thickness. Based on the results, we hypothesize that whereas Schlömann's model is valid for softly corrugated thin films, it fails to explain magnetization reversal processes of highly corrugated thin films, especially when the ripple amplitude is much greater than the deposited FM layer thickness. By means of micromagnetic simulations, we find an increase of anisotropy with thickness, just as in the experimental, as well as determine the arise of magnetic domains at the ridges of high thickness corrugated FM thin films. This approach will help to get a better understanding of operating mechanisms in magnetic field sensors based on undulated ferromagnetic materials.

TEXT

I. INTRODUCTION

Nano-undulated ferromagnetic (FM) thin films have specific magnetic properties¹ that makes them useful in applications such as Anisotropic Magnetoresistance-based magnetic field sensing² and have also recently gathered attention as promising systems within the framework of curvilinear magnetism³⁻⁷. Besides, corrugated morphologies can sustain surface-polariton excitations, forming magnetoplasmonic crystals⁸⁻¹⁰. This phenomenon enhances the reflectivity dependence on the magnetization vector, i.e., the transversal Kerr effect, improving the sensitivity over former magneto-optical field sensors up to 10^{-10} T with Signal to Noise Ratios over 10^5 as reported⁸⁻¹¹. Nano-undulation also modulates the anisotropic properties of magnetic materials and can be achieved by depositing ferromagnetic (FM) thin films onto nano-rippled substrates¹²⁻²³. Those can be fabricated using ion beam etching techniques²⁴ and are able to induce uniaxial magnetic anisotropy in isotropic materials such as Permalloy. For shallow rippled systems with ripple amplitudes of less than 20 nm^{6,25,26}, the morphology-induced anisotropy strength, related to the switching field (H_s), is bounded to an upper limit defined by Schlömann's stray-field predictions²⁷, constraining the range of application for future sensors based on this technology.

The use of Schlömann's model is valid if the magnetization vector is uniform, or its deviations from the substrate plane are small enough. Besides, the thickness must overcome the ripple amplitude so that there is, at least, a continuous plane in the structure, i.e., a non-undulated region. Such constraints allow to estimate the demagnetization fields yielding a $H_d \propto 1/t$ dependence, where H_d is dipolar field and t is film thickness. This dipolar field is related to the anisotropy field H_K , which can be estimated by a switching field H_s as Sanchez *et al* reported⁷. However, Liedke *et al*⁶ found that for softly corrugated thin magnetic films (25 nm in periodicity, 2 nm in amplitude) the evolution of the anisotropy field, does not follow Schlömann's prediction and grows linearly with the FM thickness up to a critical thickness defined by the ripple amplitude. In their experiments, this critical thickness is reached for thickness to amplitude ratios between 3 and 5. For thicker films, the anisotropy field follows Schlömann's model, and they also find a dependence of the critical thickness on the saturation magnetization, which is evidence of the dipolar origin of the magnetization reversal processes in such materials. To understand these processes, a competition of volume and surface contribution to the anisotropy has been discussed for films with a high FM thickness to ripple amplitude relation^{3,4,6}. However, the subcritical regime, where volume magnetization plays a minor role, remains unexplained up to this work.

We observed the same subcritical behavior of increasing anisotropy field with thickness in a previous work⁷ where we deposited Permalloy on nano-rippled PET substrates with higher corrugation than that reported in literature (250 nm in periodicity, 45 nm in amplitude). We found a positive correlation between switching field and FM thickness up to 50 nm within a subcritical regime, which can be exploited to improve the sensitivity and range of magnetic field sensors². However, the anisotropic behavior at FM thicknesses larger than 30 nm did not correspond to that of uniaxial anisotropy, leaving open to question the magnetization reversal mechanisms in such highly corrugated systems. For that purpose, in this work we study the magnetization reversal mechanisms present in extremely corrugated soft FM thin films (250 nm in periodicity, 180 nm in amplitude with sawtooth profile) with magnetic film thicknesses within a subcritical range (15 to 150 nm). Both experimental and simulation results yield an increasing switching field with thickness, and we propose an explanation for subcritical anisotropy behavior supported by micromagnetic simulations.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ferromagnetic (FM) nano-undulated samples were fabricated using a multistep procedure: First, a silicon wafer was nanostructured into a sawtooth (ST) profile using laser interference photolithography and reactive ion etching. Later, we grew the following materials stack: Al(2 nm)/Permalloy(t)/Al(2 nm)//Si. Permalloy (Py: $Ni_{80}Fe_{20}$) was deposited onto the sawtooth (ST) nano-patterned Si substrates using DC Sputtering ($P_{Ar} = 1 \times 10^{-5}$ bar, $P_{base} = 3 \times 10^{-10}$ bar) at normal incidence to avoid shadowing effect with different thickness t . The choice of sputtering-grown Permalloy as the FM layer has been motivated by its high degree of nano-crystallinity, which results in an isotropic behavior for all thicknesses, as opposed to epitaxially-grown thin films²⁸. Buffer and capping Aluminum layers avoid the interaction of oxygen with Permalloy, ensuring the purity and stability of the FM layer²⁹. One of the key features of this system is its elevated ripple amplitude ($\delta = 180$ nm), as it gives a wider FM thickness range below the subcritical limit and therefore allows a consistent study of the role of the morphology in the magnetic anisotropy of the system. With that aim, several ST-structured FM samples have been fabricated with Py layer thicknesses between 15 and 150 nm, named from PyST15 to PyST150 ($t = 15, 27, 35, 40, 45, 60, 75, 90, 120, 150$ nm). Twin samples were also grown onto flat Si as reference (PyF). The thickness of the films was characterized by X-Ray Reflectometry and Atomic Force Microscopy.

Nanostructured ST-Si substrates were characterized with Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FE-SEM) and by Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), see Figure 1 (a) and (b). The substrates exhibit a 2D periodic sawtooth structure with in-plane longitudinal and perpendicular axes (referred later as L.A. and P.A., respectively), defined as the directions parallel or perpendicular to the groove of the sawtooth profile, respectively. The geometric parameters of the structure according to SEM are periodicity, $p = 250$ nm; elevation angle, $\theta = 55^\circ$; ripple amplitude, $\delta = 180$ nm; and roughness, $\omega_{RMS} = \delta/2\sqrt{3} = 52$ nm. Mean profile of AFM measurements – see Figure 1 (b) – shows same periodicity as SEM although a reduced ripple amplitude ($\delta \approx 160$ nm) due to the profile being sharper than the AFM tip. Lateral SEM images of 120nm thick PyST120 sample – see Figures 1 (c) and (d) – show a good degree of conformability at high FM thicknesses, yielding a proper corrugated film.

Magnetization reversal curves of PyST and PyF samples were obtained using a custom-built vectorial Kerr magnetometer³⁰ with a polarized He-Ne laser source ($\lambda = 633$ nm). Angular reflectivity and Kerr response was gathered at 1.8° steps over a 360° circle of rotation of the samples, corresponding $\alpha = 0^\circ$ for Longitudinal Axis in PyST – see Figure 2 –, or any arbitrary position in the case of non-corrugated PyF surfaces. Incidence angle was established as $\Theta = 45^\circ$ and field was applied horizontally and parallel to P-polarized optic plane. This configuration corresponds to Longitudinal MOKE and makes it possible to obtain simultaneously Kerr rotation and Kerr reflectivity which are proportional to longitudinal ($\vec{M}_L \parallel \vec{H}$) and transversal magnetization ($\vec{M}_T \perp \vec{H}$), respectively. To improve the quality of the Kerr rotation signal (θ_{Kerr}), the reflected beam passed through a half-wave plate retarder at $\theta_{\lambda/2} \approx 22^\circ$ and a Wollaston prism prior to the register of light intensity in the Si photodetectors. Kerr experiments were carried out using alternating ($f = 11$ Hz) magnetic fields up to 200 mT.

PyST films were also modelled for micromagnetic simulations with the same geometric characteristics than the experimental samples ($p = 250$ nm, $\delta = 180$ nm). Periodic Boundary Conditions (PBC) were set 10 times in both X and Y axes to simulate a quasi-infinite XY structure. Following the same procedure as with the experimental PyST samples, hysteresis loops of different FM thick samples were simulated up to 300 nm ($t = 15, 30, 45, 60, 75, 90, 120, 150, 180, 225, 300$ nm). Typical magnetic parameters for Py³¹ ($M_s = 8.6 \times 10^5$ A/m, $A_{ex} = 13.0 \times 10^{-12}$ J/m, $K = 0$ J/m³) were used as the FM material. Note that this choice of parameters is coherent with our experimental system, given that the nanocrystalline Permalloy behaves like a uniform medium with negligible magnetic anisotropy, as aforementioned. The simulation cell size was defined as a partition of a full period of the ST structure and established at 1.95 nm, below the theoretical magnetostatic exchange length ($l_{ex} = \sqrt{2 \times A_{ex}/\mu_0/M_s^2} = 5.3$ nm for Permalloy). This ensures a proper

determination of magnetization reversal mechanisms in the micromagnetic model. Additional micromagnetic simulations were reproduced with double and half cell size (3.90 and 0.97 nm respectively) for convergence test purposes. All micromagnetic calculations were performed on GPU-based Finite-Differences software Mumax^{32,33}, which can speed up calculations by using CUDA Fast-Fourier Transform library cuFFT.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Kerr measurements of low thickness (PyST15, $t = 15 \text{ nm}$) nanopatterned sample show uniaxial anisotropy behavior (Figure 3 (a)). When magnetic field is applied parallel to the groove (referred as Longitudinal Axis: L.A.), magnetization reversal is that of a typical easy axis with coercivity $\mu_0 H_c \approx 2.5 \text{ mT}$ and reduced remanence $M_r/M_s \approx 90\%$ in the longitudinal magnetization (M_L) signal. No transversal magnetization M_T signal is found in that direction. In a complementary manner, when field is applied perpendicular to the groove (Perpendicular Axis, P.A.), magnetization reversal follows that of a Hard Axis with coercivity $\mu_0 H_c = 1.0 \text{ mT}$ and $M_r/M_s \approx 5\%$ in M_L . One should notice that the transversal magnetization M_T in P.A. has a transversal remanence ($M_T(H = 0)/M_s$) of 33%, smaller than the expected value for an ideal hard axis (100%). This suggests that the magnetization reversal process involves both coherent rotation and domain nucleation, and it indicates that the system is stable at magnetic fields close to zero. The transversal magnetization also allows the definition of a switching field H_s , as the field where the transversal magnetization crosses zero. This switching field is related to the anisotropy strength of the system as it sets the field at which the magnetization undergoes a change of tendency and serves to estimate the range of application of former magnetic field sensors^{2,8-10} as well as the anisotropy of non-typical magnetic systems without a well-defined hard-axis. The uniaxial behavior of PyST15 is maintained at 27 nm FM thick as in PyST27 (see Figure 3 (b)), with hard axis behavior at P.A. and easy-like axis behavior at L.A., although its remanence is reduced from 90% to 80%. At FM thicknesses of 40nm or larger, the uniaxial anisotropy character of PyST systems vanishes. Hysteresis loops of PyST40 (Figure 3 (c)), reveal hard axis like behavior in both P.A. and L.A., as opposed with less thick samples where L.A. behaved as an easy axis (see Figures 3 (a) and (b)). Both longitudinal magnetization M_L components in P.A. and L.A. are more hysteretic than the 15nm counterpart, and the remanent transversal magnetization M_T is smaller as well. The transition from easy axis to hard axis in the Longitudinal Axis is further evidenced in thicker samples as 60 nm thick PyST60 (see Figure 3 (d)). For this thickness, the remanence at L.A. drops to values of less than 10%, while the transversal remanence is reduced significantly to around 0.2%, suggesting a major role of domain formation in the system as FM thickness increases.

Angular measurements of 15nm and 27nm nanopatterned samples (PyST15 and PyST27 respectively) yield coercivity H_c distributions specific of uniaxial anisotropic systems (Figure 4 (a)). In both systems coercivity reaches a minimum of $\mu_0 H_c \approx 1.0 \text{ mT}$ at P.A. ($\alpha = 90^\circ$) and a maximum $\mu_0 H_c \approx 4.5 \text{ mT}$ at $\alpha = 105^\circ$ (15° from P.A.). However, the intermediate values differ between PyST15 and PyST27 samples, being larger for PyST27. Angular measurements of 27 nm thick flat PyF27 sample are set as reference and show small coercivity values ranging from 0.25 to 0.55 mT without a clear anisotropy axis (Figure 4 (a)), and therefore isotropic-like behavior. This proves that the anisotropy of the corrugated samples is entirely due to the magnetostatic contribution of the nanopattern on where the FM layer is deposited, boosting H_c 10 times over the flat sample. Angular dependence of switching field H_s estimates of PyST15 and PyST27 show an elongated astroid distribution, see Figure 4 (b), with minimums at L.A. of $\mu_0 H_s \approx 2.5 \text{ mT}$. The major difference between both systems is found at P.A. ($\alpha = 90^\circ$), with a larger switching field for PyST27 ($\mu_0 H_s \approx 21 \text{ mT}$) than for PyST15 ($\mu_0 H_s \approx 13 \text{ mT}$). This indicates an increase on the magnetic anisotropy strength with the FM thickness that is confirmed in thicker samples.

A further insight on the FM thickness dependence of the magnetic anisotropy can be achieved by comparing switching fields H_s of our samples measured at P.A., see Figure 5 (a). We observe that the magnetic anisotropy of our system grows with the FM thickness. It's also shown the expected dependence of the dipolar field strength as in nano-undulated systems can be derived from Schlömann's model of stray dipolar fields²⁷ given by Equation [1], where μ_0 is magnetic susceptibility, H_d is dipolar field, M_s is magnetization saturation, ω_{rms} is roughness, p is periodicity and t is FM layer thickness. As derived from Equation [1], the model predicts a lower dipolar field as the FM thickness is increased and thus a loss of magnetic anisotropy.

$$\mu_0 H_d (mT) = \mu_0 M_s \left(\frac{A}{m} \right) \frac{2\pi \omega_{rms}^2}{p t} \quad [1]$$

We observe a striking difference between experimental H_s and the dipolar field H_d derived from Schlömann's model. This has also been found in literature^{6,7,14} but not at such highly corrugated systems as ours ($\delta = 180nm$), being the values reported in the $\delta = 2 - 50 nm$ range. Such studies report a critical thickness for which the switching field reaches a maximum and decreases thereon, following the dipolar field dependence derived from Schlömann's model¹¹. The behavior is similar but, in our case, the critical thickness is not yet reached even at 150 nm. The lack of critical thickness could be due to the high corrugation, but we also observe a loss in the uniaxial character for thicknesses above 40 nm, meaning that the uniaxial anisotropy hypothesis is no longer valid indicating a possibly different origin for the linear behavior and the change in the magnetization reversal.

The anisotropic behavior of the system within the subcritical regime can be understood by means of volume and surface dipolar contributions to the anisotropy of the system^{3,6,7}:

$$\mu_0 H_s t (mT \cdot nm) = \mu_0 H_s^V t + 2\mu_0 H_s^S \quad [2]$$

where H_s is switching field for Perpendicular Axis, H_s^V and H_s^S are volume and surface contributions, and t is FM thickness. Figure 5 (b) shows linear fits of $\mu_0 H_s \cdot t$ to determine H_s^V and H_s^S values from the slope and y-intercept respectively. Thus, we can define two magnetization regimes with FM thickness (shown as blue and red fits) based on the competition between H_s^V and H_s^S : For thinner films ($t < 60 nm$, dashed blue line), where the corrugation of the system largely exceeds the FM thickness, surface pole strength rules the magnetization reversal mechanism. In this case, the surficial term magnitude surpasses the volume anisotropy by near a factor of 10 ($\mu_0 H_s^V \approx 40 mT$, $\mu_0 H_s^S \approx -300 mT$). For thicker FM films ($t > 60nm$, in dashed orange line), the volumetric anisotropy increases (as evidenced by the steeper slope), but it also does the absolute value of the surface anisotropy ($\mu_0 H_s^V \approx 300 mT$, $\mu_0 H_s^S \approx -8000 mT$). Since the increase of volume anisotropy is expected with the FM thickness, the larger surface anisotropy fields for very thick layers can be explained by a totally different magnetization scheme due to the formation of magnetic domains. This change in the magnetic behavior of the system with thicknesses above 60 nm is in good agreement with the noticeable loss of the uniaxial anisotropy of the system for FM thicknesses greater than 40 nm, indicating a gradual change in the anisotropy tradeoff. To fully understand the magnetization reversal of our subcritical corrugated PyST FM films, micromagnetic simulations have been performed, as they include the magnetostatics contributions self consistently.

IV. SIMULATIONS

The simulations of magnetization reversal loops demonstrate uniaxial-like anisotropic behavior in magnetization reversal hysteresis loops of samples at FM thicknesses of less than 90 nm. As in the experimental counterpart, at low thicknesses easy and hard axes [Figure 6 (a)] are found in the L.A and P.A. of the nanopattern. Figure 6 (a) shows the calculated longitudinal magnetization (M_L) and transversal magnetization (M_T) for a 15 nm thick PyST15 simulated sample. We can also define a switching field H_s as we did in the experimental. The dependence of switching field H_s with FM layer thickness is shown in Figure 6 (b), and as in the experimental results, H_s follows an increasing trend with FM thickness. Nevertheless, for FM thicknesses

close to the ripple amplitude ($\delta = 180 \text{ nm}$), H_s collapses down to low values of less than 10 mT , and in no case follows the predicted dipolar field H_d evolution derived from Schlömann's model. This indicates that the model is not able to capture the behavior at high corrugation.

In the Longitudinal Axis [Figure 6 (c)], a transition from Easy to Hard-like Axis is found as the FM layer increases, with magnetization crossover at moderate magnetic fields (10-30 mT), indicating better reversibility. On the other hand, the Perpendicular Axis [Figure 6 (d)] has hysteresis at high FM thickness ($t \geq 90 \text{ nm}$), showing that its magnetic behavior differs from that of uniaxial anisotropy. This reversal mechanism is observed in our experimental data, i.e., the hysteretic behavior of thick samples ($t \geq 40 \text{ nm}$) along P.A., as well as the transition from easy to hard-like Axis behavior in the L.A. as depicted in Figure 3. However, we observed the transition at 40 nm, and simulations predict it at 90 nm FM thick. This discrepancy may be attributed to the presence of defects^{7,12,25} or reduced M_s of sputtered materials which might reduce the demagnetizing field³⁴. The latter hypothesis has been tested by micromagnetic simulations (Figure 6 (b)), showing that the reduction of M_s increases the critical thickness, indicating that the defects can significantly alter the magnetic reversal path in highly corrugated system.

The increase in anisotropy is related to that reported by Liedke et. al.⁶ in smoothly corrugated ($\delta = 2.5 \text{ nm}$) rippled magnetic films. In such system the critical thickness t_{crit} was inversely proportional to M_s , as their Permalloy samples ($M_s = 8.6 \times 10^5 \text{ A/m}$) have $t_{py,crit} = 12 \text{ nm}$, while Cobalt samples ($M_s = 1.4 \times 10^6 \text{ A/m}$) present $t_{Co,crit} = 7.5 \text{ nm}$. We have found that is also present in high thickness FM thin films, provided the FM layer does not surpass a critical thickness related to the ripple amplitude of the substrate.

The micromagnetic distribution at remanence drawn from P.A. hysteresis loops is shown in Figure 7 (see Fig. 7 (a) as reference for micromagnetic moment color and orientation). We can see that in the uniaxial regime ($t = 60 \text{ nm}$, Fig.7 (b)) the micromagnetic moments follow the Longitudinal-Easy Axis at remanence due to a coherent rotation magnetization reversal, just as expected from a Hard Axis. When the FM layer thickness equals the ripple amplitude ($t = \delta = 180 \text{ nm}$, Fig.7 (c)), the remanent magnetization follows the sawtooth contour, bounded by magnetic domains in the corners with magnetization parallel to the Longitudinal Axis separated by Néel domain walls. This behavior is found in thicknesses from 90nm and marks the ending of the subcritical uniaxial-like regime, as the magnetization reversal mechanism does not correspond to that of uniaxial anisotropies.

Finally, at large FM thicknesses ($t = 300 \text{ nm}$, Fig. 7 (d)), the remanent distribution shows a middle band of magnetization following the Perpendicular Axis, with bottom and top magnetic domains oriented towards or against Longitudinal Axis, respectively, in an arrangement that resembles to a cross-tie type wall. The appearance of dipolar-coupled antiparallel regions and the change of the domain wall indicates a non-straightforward relationship between FM thickness and magnetic anisotropy that is beyond the scope of this article.

Given that such domain walls minimize magnetostatic energy and avoid the formation of magnetic poles, they show that the dipolar based Schlömann's approach is not suitable for a system with these characteristics, i.e., with low FM thickness to amplitude ratio.

V. CONCLUSIONS

We observe an increasing switching field with ferromagnetic layer thickness in a wide thickness range up to 150 nm in highly corrugated ferromagnetic thin films. This switching field as it estimates the anisotropy field of the system, behaves against the expected dipolar field prediction of Schlömann's model. It has also been found a transition at 40 nm thick where the magnetic behavior no longer follows that of uniaxial anisotropy, related to an anisotropy tradeoff between surface and volume contributions, and yielding to a more complicated domain-wall based magnetization from 60 nm and up. This change of behavior has been found in micromagnetic simulations, showing that, although the magnetic behavior has a dipolar origin and thus is

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strictly related to the saturation, the anisotropy dependence with ferromagnetic thickness does not follow Schlömann's predictions. This can be explained by the arise of magnetic domains at the ridges of thick films that minimize the formation of magnetic dipoles. It has also been found thickness dependent magnetic domains, transitioning from parallel to antiparallel configuration at high thicknesses. These results demonstrate that the traditional dipolar based approaches are incomplete in highly corrugated thick samples.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Data Availability

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Authors Contributions (CRediT authorship contribution statement)

Rafael Delgado-Garcia: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization. Gabriel Rodriguez-Rodriguez: Investigation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing - review & editing, Visualization, Supervision. Ruben Guerrero: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision. Fernando Galvez: Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing. Jose M. Colino: Conceptualization, Validation, Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Supervision.

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Figure 1. (a) Lateral FE-SEM image of nano-patterned ST Si wafer. The sawtooth contour defines a 2D periodic structure with Longitudinal (L.A.) and Perpendicular (P.A.) axes and geometric parameters: periodicity p and ripple amplitude δ . (b) AFM characterization of ST Si wafer. Bottom right: AFM mean profile of the ST Si wafer showing measured 250nm in periodicity and $\sim 160\text{nm}$ in ripple amplitude. (c) Lateral FE-SEM image of 120nm thick PyST sample showing good conformability of the sputtered FM film. (d) Lateral FE-SEM image of backscattered electrons of 120nm thick PyST sample highlighting the heavier elements (Fe and Ni) of the FM layer.

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Figure 2. Schematic of Longitudinal MOKE setup: A P-polarized 632.8nm laser beam reflects in the Ferromagnetic sample at 45° incidence angle. The polarization of the reflected beam is rotated to 45° through a rotatable half-wave plate and P and S resulting polarizations are separated in a Wollaston Prism prior to their gathering in two Si photodiodes. Magnetic field \vec{H} is applied horizontally and parallel to the optical plane. The FM sample can be rotated, defining an angle (α) between its Longitudinal Axis (L.A.) and the magnetic field direction. This configuration enables the simultaneous characterization of longitudinal (M_L) and transverse magnetizations (M_T) since they are proportional to gathered Kerr rotation and reflectivity, respectively.

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Figure 3. Hysteresis loops of 15nm thick PyST15 (a), 27nm thick PyST27 (b), 40nm thick PyST40 (c), and 60nm thick PyST60 (d) nanopatterned samples in both Longitudinal and Perpendicular axes (L.A. and P.A., respectively). M_L refers to longitudinal magnetization while M_T refers to transversal magnetization. Transversal magnetization of PyST60 at Perpendicular Axis is magnified 20 times. FE-SEM image of ST substrate with L.A. and P.A. is shown as reference.

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Figure 4. Angular plots of coercive field $\mu_0 H_c$ (a) of 15 nm and 27 nm thick PyST15 and PyST27, along with 27 nm thick flat PyF27 sample; and switching field H_s (b) of PyST15 and PyST27. AFM image of ST substrate with angle α between applied field and L.A. is shown as reference.

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Figure 5. (a) Switching field evolution with FM thickness estimated from Kerr measurements at Perpendicular Axis (blue). A black dashed line represents the FM thickness at which the systems does not longer behave as uniaxial. Dashed purple and green lines represent anisotropy evolution with FM thicknesses below and above 60nm, respectively. The red curve depicts Schlömann's dipolar field prediction for a system with the features of our samples. (b) Linear fit of $H_s \cdot t$ and confidence intervals ($1\sigma = 68.2\%$) for volume and surface anisotropy estimation, see Equation 2. Experimental data from Kerr measurements at Perpendicular Axis is plotted in blue, while purple and orange lines correspond to linear adjustments for thicknesses below and above 60 nm, respectively. Volume anisotropy is estimated from the slope of the line, while surface anisotropy is from y-intercept. Inset shows the thin film ($t < 60$ nm) region.

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Figure 6. (a) Magnetization reversal curves of simulated 15nm PyST15 in Perpendicular Axis (P.A.) and Longitudinal Axis (L.A.) with longitudinal magnetization (M_L) and transversal magnetization (M_T) components. Switching field is defined as zero-crossing transversal magnetization, (b) Simulated switching field of PyST systems in P.A. as function of film thickness with full and half saturation magnetization (green and yellow, respectively). Calculated dipolar field from Schlömann's prediction is shown in red as comparison, as well as experimental results in blue., (c) Simulated longitudinal magnetization reversal curves of PyST films in Longitudinal Axis (L.A.), (d) Simulated longitudinal magnetization reversal curves of PyST films in Perpendicular Axis (P.A.).

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Figure 7. Micromagnetic moment distribution following HSL color scale (a) at remanence from saturation in Perpendicular Axis ($P.A. \parallel \vec{H}$) at different FM thicknesses: (b) 60 nm, (c) 180 nm, (d) 300 nm. Red arrows follow Perpendicular Axis, while white and black follow the sawtooth contour upwards and downwards, respectively. Green and purple follow the Longitudinal Axis ($L.A. \perp \vec{H}$) in ingoing and outgoing directions respectively, arranging magnetic domains in the ridges and valleys for 180nm and 300nm thicknesses.

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Legend for (c) and (d): PyST15 (black square), PyST30 (purple square), PyST45 (blue square), PyST60 (light blue square), PyST90 (green triangle), PyST150 (yellow triangle), PyST225 (orange circle).

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